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HTTTC CONFERENCE 2025 PROCEEDINGS

SCIENCE OF EDUCATION

PARENTING STYLES AND ITS EFFECTS ON STUDENT MISCONDUCT IN SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN THE BUEA MUNICIPALITY

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Abstract

This study sought to investigate Parenting styles and its effect on Students' Misconduct in secondary schools in Buea Municipality. The following research objectives guided the study: To investigate the effect of authoritarian parenting style on Students' Misconduct in secondary schools, to examine the effect of permissive parenting style on Students' Misconduct in secondary Schools in Buea Municipality and to investigate the effect of uninvolved parenting style on Students' Misconduct in secondary schools in Buea Municipality. The researcher then transformed the research objectives into research questions and Hypotheses. The study made use of the quantitative method precisely, the cross-sectional research design. The population of the study was made up of 17,535 students with 476 students being the sample which was done using the simple random sampling technique. Data was collected using closed ended questionnaire. The inferential statistical tool used was the chi-square. Data collected from the field using questionnaire (quantitative data) were analysed using SPSS version 27 and presented using descriptive statistics on tables, scattered plot, frequency and percentages. The overall coefficient value of the questionnaire on reliability was 0.886. It was concluded that, Parenting Style has an effect on Students' Misconduct in secondary schools in the Buea Municipality. The findings revealed that 63.6% of students accept that authoritarian parenting style is used by their parent which affect students' misconduct while 36.4% disagreed (R-value 0.720**, p-value 0.000 < 0.05) For permissive parenting style 48.8% of students agreed that permissive parenting affects students' Misconduct while 51.2% disagreed (R-value 0.747**, p-value 0.000 < 0.05). 53.7% of students accept that uninvolved parenting style affect students' misconduct while 46.3% disagreed (R-value 0.751**, p-value 0.000 < 0.05). The study recommended that, parents should create clear expectations for their children, give them opportunities to explore while being guided and create unconditional love towards their children so that they develop high self-esteem, empathy and emotional balance.

Keywords: Parenting, Parenting Styles, Authoritarian Parenting, Permissive Parenting, Uninvolved Parenting, Misconduct and Students' Misconduct

1. Introduction

The way parents shape their children's behaviour has been a long-standing source of concern by philosophers, scientists and even parents themselves. Children learn more quickly during their early years than at any other time in life. Young children grow and learn when they receive love, affection, attention, encouragement and mental stimulation, as well as nutritious meals and good health care from parents, caregivers and older siblings.

Parenting styles and the quality of a parent-child relationship may influence the behaviour and conduct of children. A child's emotion, autonomy, behaviour and identity are all referred to as part of psychological development which takes place throughout life (Erikson, 1968). Developing a secure positive self-esteem and positive interactions with others and control over one's feelings during childhood is vital to good moral development. It is important to take into consideration the overall parenting style when understanding the effects, the parenting behaviour has on a child's conduct and behaviour.

A child's conduct be it through discipline, respect of school rules and regulations, norms and social interaction are greatly influenced by the type of parenting style used by their parents so as to determine their behaviour. It is for this reason that the researcher lays a lot of emphasis on the effect of parenting styles on students' misconduct. Hence, the purpose of this paper is to examine how parenting styles influence students' misconduct in secondary schools in Buea Municipality.

Over the years, Students have always portrayed normal or desirable conducts as they were punctual in class, obedient, honest, respectful, and decent and had the fear of God which made them to excel well in their studies and be seen as well cultured and acceptable members of the society. Nowadays, this is not the case with the behaviour of students in schools and society as the rate of misconduct is rampant in our societies today. Most students exhibit behaviours such as stealing, disobedience, lack of respect, bullying and dishonesty, which cause them to be distracted from studies, thereby leading to poor performance, unattainable stated objectives and seen as unacceptable members of the society. Misconduct portrayed by students in Cameroon in general and Buea in particular has been on an increase even after all the interventions from teachers, school administrators and counsellors. Nowadays it is discovered that parents shift their attention from their children to their occupations. They have little or no time to educate and train their children on norms, values and customs governing the society because of their busy work schedules. This makes students to listen to their peers more since they are always available than their parents, hence, imitate their undesired behaviours by portraying misconducts in schools as a result

of poor or inadequate parenting leading to ineffective learning. It is based on these shortcomings that this study has been designed to examine how the different parenting styles affect students' Misconduct in secondary schools in Buea Municipality. This problem leads to the following research questions: To what extent does Parenting Styles affect Students' Misconduct in Secondary Schools in Buea Municipality? Specifically, to what extent does Authoritarian Parenting style affect Students' Misconduct in Secondary Schools in Buea Municipality? How does Permissive Parenting style affect Students' Misconduct in Secondary Schools in Buea Municipality? To what extent does Uninvolved Parenting style affect Students' Misconduct in Secondary Schools in Buea Municipality? The following corresponding hypotheses were formulated:

Ho: Parenting Styles has no significant effect on Students' Misconduct in Secondary Schools in Buea Municipality.

Ha: Parenting Styles has a significant effect on Students' Misconduct in Secondary Schools in Buea Municipality.

2. Literature Review

The relevant literature related to the study will be presented under the conceptual review which are parenting, parenting styles, authoritarian parenting, permissive parenting, uninvolved parenting, misconduct and students' misconduct. theoretical review which are Diana Baumrind's theory of parenting styles and Albert Bandura's Social Cognitive Theory and empirical review which are authoritarian parenting on students' misconduct, permissive parenting on students' misconduct and uninvolved parenting on students' misconduct.

a. Conceptual Review

Parenting

Parenting may be defined as purposive activities aimed at ensuring the survival and development of children. It derives from the Latin verb "parere" "to bring forth, develop or educate". The word parenting from its root is more concerned with the activity of developing and educating than who does it (Clarke & Stewart, 2006). Parenting is a positive, nurturing activity. Thus, parenting is an activity that normally involves the children, parents and other family members in lifelong interaction. Jane (2012) equally highlighted that Parenting or child up bringing is the process of promoting and supporting the physical,

emotional, social, and intellectual development of a child from infancy to adulthood. development and wellbeing.

According to Bradley and Wildman (2002), parenting refers to the ability of a parent to instigate and facilitate a child's optimal development, in a safe environment, while preserving healthy relationships with others. Wessel (2005) further avers that parenting is a process of instilling learning and social skills, through the interaction with their children. Therefore, parental practices (by either parents or caregivers) play a pivotal role in children's upbringing, and significantly influence their functioning toward skills acquisition. Teaching manners and etiquettes are critical part of informal education. In Africa, it is called home training. Parenting is not a workout or physical exercise. Parenting in the family cannot be over emphasized when bringing up a child. Every adult is the end product of the success or failure of their parent as regards to home training (Tawose, 2022).

How children are taught or teach themselves to become competent members of their communities varies across cultures. Bornstein (2013) concurs that parents raise their children, according to their indigenous cultural belief systems and behaviour patterns, as practiced in their society. According to Bornstein (2013), this parenting practice scaffolds children to become culturally competent members of their society, by adhering to what is socially acceptable. According to Perrino et al. (2000), parents through their teaching role, set limits for specific behaviour, or discipline their children, and ultimately model healthy, competent behaviour to them. Therefore, when children display socially unacceptable behaviour, the tendency is to locate the problem at the doorstep of parents and the family. This implies that the behaviour of the child is as a reflection of the parents, or the family in which the child was born. Wanjohi (2013) revealed that parenting practices have a huge impact on the child, including the child's brain development, success, personality enhancement, school performance and good peer relationships. Therefore, this implies that parenting practices at home affect the manner in which the child acquire skills, behaves and conducts him/herself in the society.

Parenting and child rearing are concepts often used interchangeably. Woodcock (2003) elucidates that parenting is the ability of a parent to care for the child's needs, which includes emotional, physical, social and spiritual, to assist in promoting the child's well-being. Brooks (2012), as well as Faircloth et al. (2013) concurs that parenting involves the parents' ability to influence the child's development, including the physical, emotion, social ability, morality and intelligence.

Parenting Styles

According to Yan et al. (2022), parenting style is defined as a representation of parents' attitudes and behaviours toward children as well as the emotional climate of a family as a result of parents' behaviour and attitude. From this definition, one can see that parenting styles play a critical role in a child's emotional, cognitive, and behavioural development. Parenting styles can greatly influence one's motivation and creativity, especially during earlier childhood (Seyed et al., 2015).

When children are over-controlled by their parents, they experience pressure to think, feel, or behave in particular ways. Children's self-esteem would be negatively affected, which in turn limits creativity (Koestner et al., 2010). Therefore, parenting styles reflect the essence of parent-child communication and play an important role in the development of individual creativity (Bradford et al., 2004; Wang et al., 2007).

A parenting style is the overall emotional climate in the home. Darling and Steinberg (1993) defined parenting style as a construct representing standard strategies parents use in raising their children. A child's upbringing according to Fieldsman (1996) is a consequence of the child rearing philosophy that the parent hold, the specific practices they employ and the nature of their own and children's personality. However, the kind of temperament a baby is born with may in part elicit kinds of parental child-rearing style. Baumrind (1978) identified three main parenting styles in early child development which are authoritative, authoritarian, and permissive. These parenting styles were later expanded to four, including an uninvolved style. On the one hand, these four styles of parenting involve combinations of acceptance and responsiveness, and on the other hand, involve demand and control (Baumrind, 1971). The area of parents, their parenting styles and how these styles affect or impact child development has long been the interest of many scholars. However, finding actual cause-and-effect links between specific styles of parenting and later behaviour of children is very difficult. Some children raised in dramatically different environments can later grow up to have remarkably similar personalities. Conversely, children who share a home and are raised in the same environment can grow up to have astonishingly different personalities than one another. Despite these challenges, researchers have uncovered convincing links between parenting styles and the effects these styles have on children. The concept of parenting styles was developed by Baumrind (1967). However, Daniel and Steinberg (2003) defined parenting style as "a constellation of parental behaviours and attitudes toward their children that are conveyed to the children and that, as a whole, create an emotional bond in which the parents' behaviour ours are expressed".

The relevance of these styles and practices in the socialization and developmental outcomes of children cannot be overemphasized. This is because, parents across cultures have unique socialization goals, such as helping their child become an autonomous, self-reliant individual or a socially interdependent individual. The socialization goals shape parents' everyday interactions and parenting styles with their children. Parents in Western cultures endorse autonomous socialization goals that focus on helping their children become independent, competitive, and self-expressive, while parents in Asian cultures emphasize obedience, respect, and social interdependence (Keller & Otto, 2009; Barnhart et al., 2013).

In many traditional African communities, parenting occurs within a collectivist environment of kin and community networks (Amos, 2013; Bray & Dawes, 2016; Brudevold-Newman et al., 2018; Degbey, 2012). According to Green et al. (2005), collectivism is characterized by a high level of interdependence, and is associated with a sense of duty toward one's group. In the context of family, collectivism manifests in the form of behavioural attitudes and adherence to norms or demands of in-groups such as the extended family. For Degbey (2012), the extended family system is made up of several generations that may include parents and their children, grandparents, uncles, and aunts and cousins, all living in one homestead or close to one another. In this context, the notion of parenthood cannot solely be the responsibility of a child's parents. Instead, brothers of a child's father are considered to be in the position of the biological father, whilst the wives of the father's brothers are equally in the position of the biological mother (Houzel, 1999). This means that a child knows his or her biological father and mother, but also acknowledges that several adults related to him or her are also social parents who play a parental role.

It is therefore expected in this context that every adult has a responsibility to play an educational role in relation to a child, even if they are not the biological parents of that child. In this situation, education takes a collective and social character that makes it the responsibility not only of the family, but also of members of the same village or neighbourhood (Amos, 2013). In other words, the pressure that most Western parents face in order to be seen as good parents is likely to dissipate in the role-sharing arrangement that is created by the African extended family system. One segment of the extended family in the African community that plays an important role in parenting is grandparents. Unlike parents, their role is not to exercise authority but to transmit values, skills, and family history (Hummel & Perrenoud, 2009).

Parenting is the process of raising and educating a child from birth or before until adulthood (Self Growth, 2012). Synonymously, parenting refers to carrying out the responsibilities of raising and relating to children in such a manner that the child is well prepared to realize

his or her full potential as a human being. This implies that parenting is the process of taking care or supporting a child from birth to adulthood involving the physical, emotional, social and intellectual capabilities. It can simply mean the process or state of being a parent. In fact, one can be a parent both to the biological or non-biological children.

According to Baumrind (1967), there are four major styles of parenting. The researchers argue that majority of the parents display one of four different parenting styles. These styles are authoritarian parenting, authoritative parenting, permissive parenting and uninvolved parenting.

According to Cherry (2012), authoritarian parenting style expect the child to adhere or follow the strict rules established by the parents. Failure to follow the rules will result in punishment. Usually, because the parents have ordered, it must be done without explanations and questions. On the other hand, authoritative parents establish rules and guidelines that their children are expected to follow. Nevertheless, this parenting style is much more democratic (Cherry, 2012 & Santrock, 2006). Parents with this style are responsive and ready to listen and cooperate. Baumrind (1991) argues that these parents are assertive but not intrusive and restrictive.

Santrock (2006) also stated that permissive parents have few demands to make of their children. These parents allow their children a lot of freedom. They hardly punish or discipline them (Baumrind, 1991) while uninvolved parenting is attributed with few demands and little communication. Though the parents fulfil the needs of the child, they rarely get attached to the child (Cherry, 2012). Similarly, uninvolved parents make few to no demands of their children and they are often indifferent, dismissive or even completely neglectful.

Authoritarian Parenting Styles

They are the type of parenting styles in which parents are often strict and harsh. They are flexible to the child's needs and enforce reasonable standards of conduct (Ang & Goh, 2006). Authoritarian parents show little affection to their children. The parents under this parenting style do not consider the children's opinion as a group, and discourage verbal give and-take. Obedience, respect, and tradition are highly valued. Rules are non-negotiable; parents are always right and disobedient children are often punished physically (Berger, 2001). Authoritarian parents also expect a level of maturity higher than the norm for their child's particular age group.

Authoritarian parenting follows a rather dictatorial style involving the highest degree of control on children and very low levels of warmth. Parents who adopt such styles expect strong obedience from their children and favour punitive discipline in response to acts of rebellion (Kang & Moore, 2011; Hong, 2012). They are usually found setting strict rules to abide by and monitoring their child's time as well as their activities during the day and night. Moreover, the use of this authoritarian style precludes effective discussion, of any sort, between parents and children, which places more pressure on the children than any other parenting style (Areepattamannil, 2010; Hong, 2012).

Permissive Parenting Styles

They rarely enforce rules for their children to follow. They are different from authoritarian parents as they practice high level of nurturance and clarity of communication while exercising low level of control and maturity demands (Sarac, 2001). These parents are indulgent, not wanting to impose their will on their children. They might cause their children to avoid even natural or logical consequences in order to save them from perceived harm, unhappiness or hurt. Permissive parents are usually kind and loving, may become frustrated, when a child's behaviour is deviant or unacceptable. Permissive parents do not often step into, or cause change in the child's action as long as he will not be physically harmed. Permissive parents encourage autonomy and decision making by their children. These parents rarely discipline their children because they have relatively low expectations and self-control. Permissive parents are generally nurturing and communicative with their children, often taken on the status of a friend more than that of a parent. Permissive parents take orders and instructions from their children.

Uninvolved Parenting

They are sometimes referred to as neglectful parenting, indifferent parenting, or unresponsive parenting. "Uninvolved parenting is a parenting style in which a parent does not meet the needs of their child. The parent provides little guidance, discipline, responsiveness, or nurturance to the child. (Wendy Wisner, 2022). The uninvolved parent may show limited to no awareness of circumstances that pertain to the child and their emotional presence might be described as empty, cold, or neglectful with unloving and uncaring behaviours towards the child. Uninvolved parents may show a lack of atonement to the child's emotional state, they may neglect to make any rules at home, and they may demand little in terms of their child's behaviour and growth. Examples of uninvolved parenting include ignoring a child when they attempt to speak to you, showing a lack of interest in your child's passions (sports, art, books, friendships, etc.), and not expressing

genuine love or care for your child, explains Dr. Downey. Uninvolved parents are more likely to leave their children unsupervised than other parents (Maccobay & Martin, 1983).

The uninvolved parenting style is the one most likely to have negative effects on children. Although many children brought up by uninvolved parents become independent, they often do so out of necessity and as a means of survival. Uninvolved parents are like permissive parents in their failure to enforce standards. But unlike permissive parents, uninvolved parents are not nurturing and warm. They provided kids with food and shelter, but not much else (Maccoby & Martin, 1983).

Conduct

Conduct refers to the performance of a person either all the times or at a particular event typically as it acclimates to or veers away from societal status quos (Sam, 2023). Conduct is often associated with behaviours that are considered acceptable or appropriate in a given context or society. It involves adherence to principles, rules or standards of behaviour that are typically established by a group, organization or society. For instance, a person's conduct can refer to their honesty, discipline, integrity, compliance with established rules and regulations, obedience and respect (Driest, 2016).

Misconduct

misconduct refers to any activity or behaviour portrayed by an individual or group of individuals which impairs other people's freedom to pursue their studies, harmful to the good order and government of the institution, seen as undesirable and unacceptable behaviour in that institution (Ives & Nehrkorn, 2019). Examples of misconduct include fighting, stealing, disobedience, indecency, examination malpractices and promotion manipulation.

Students' Misconduct

Students' Misconduct refers to all the undesirable, unwanted and unacceptable behaviours and actions portrayed by students which is against the school rules and regulations (Adesile et al., 2016). Also, all wrongful, improper, or unlawful conduct motivated by premeditated or intentional purpose or by obstinate indifference to the consequences of one's acts. It is an act portrayed by a student or group of students which is unacceptable by the school which may cause harm to another students' health or well-being and that of the teachers (Owunwanne et al., 2010). Examples of Students' misconduct are bullying, stealing, fighting, stabbing, disobedience and indecency.

Also, Students' Misconduct refers to any fraudulent actions or attempts by a student within the educational institution which is against the rules and regulations of the school (Theart & Smit, 2012). An example of student misconduct in schools today is academic dishonesty which refers to attempt portrayed by students to present others' academic work as their own (Jensen et al., 2001). Another example of student misconduct is cheating which has two forms, which is cheating behaviour such as copying answers of others and plagiarizing behaviour such as citing without including the correct source. According to Craig and Dalton (2013), plagiarism includes intentional and unintentional actions in utilizing another person's work wrongly. It is conducted in the form of replicating another person's work, copying the whole text, or even buying another person's writing and then admitting it as one's own. It also refers an inaccurate and non-thorough behaviour in quoting, citing, and reporting the source being used dishonestly (Spielberger, 2004).

Cheating which is a form of student misconduct is defined by Salkind (2008), as a dishonest action with the element of deceiving with the goal of obtaining benefits or superiority from other students. Anderman et al. (2009) described cheating as four categories which are information transfer between individuals, the use of assisting tools, exploitation of weakness, and copying answers or information. Cizek (2012) defined academic cheating as any action taken before, during, or after the administration of a test and assignments that is intended to gain an unfair advantage or produce inaccurate results.

b. Theoretical Framework

i. Diana Baumrind Theory of Parenting Styles (1966)

Baumrind is widely considered to be the pioneer of introducing parental style and control – authoritarian, authoritative, and permissive.

This style of parenting is more associated with positive adolescent outcomes. As a result, it is found as most beneficial and effective style of parenting among most of the families. Therefore, children and adolescents will flourish if parents exercise authoritative parenting. In other words, authoritative parenting style fosters positive well-being of adolescents.

Authoritarian parents exhibit low responsiveness and they are highly demanding. In this style of parenting, parents emphasize on conformity and obedience and thus expect that they are obeyed without explanation in a less warm environment. Furthermore, authoritarian parents display low level of engagement and trust toward their children (Santrock, 2009). They most often discourage open communication and make strict control of a child's behaviour. In other words, it is widely believed that an authoritarian parent is

forceful, punitive and believes that a child should adhere to work in accordance to ethics and should be obedient.

In the authoritarian parenting style, parents are more concerned with the traditional family structure; therefore, they limit the child's autonomy along with the parent-child relationship. Since the foremost concern of this parenting style rests within the traditional family structure, the child is demanded to adhere to parent's orders without any questions; therefore, it can be argued that authoritarian parenting style tends to rely on rules that are considered as concrete (Holden, 2010). According to Baumrind (1966), permissive parents attempt to behave in acceptant, affirmative and non-punitive manner toward their children's impulses, actions and desires. In addition, they tend to avoid engaging in behavioural control, do not set rules and set a small number of behavioural expectations for their adolescents. From this perspective, it can be stated that permissive parents actually allow the adolescents to actively participate without being concerned for their actions.

This theory is very timely in this study because it is widely believed that the delinquent behaviour in most of the juveniles is the result of parenting styles. For example, adolescents can be led towards delinquent behaviour when they are exposed to lack of intimacy, lack of guidance, lack of parental involvement, lack of parental attachment, anger and blaming. It would therefore not be wrong to state that there is a significant link between the parental styles and individual's tendency to engage in delinquent or violent behaviour (Baumrind, 1991).

ii. *Social Cognitive Theory by Bandura, A. (1986)*

Bandura developed the Social Cognitive Theory based on the concept that learning is affected by cognitive, behavioural, and environmental factors, which means that the environment, behaviour, and cognitive factors all interact as determinants of each other (Bandura, 1991). In contrast to the traditional psychological theories that emphasized learning through direct experience, Bandura posited that virtually all learning phenomena can occur by observing other people's behaviour and consequence of it (Bandura, 1986). Social cognitive theory has often been called a bridge between behavioural and cognitive learning theories, because it focuses on the interaction between internal factors such as thinking and symbolic processing (e.g., attention, memory, motivation) and external determinants (e.g., rewards and punishments) in determining behaviour.

3. Methodology

This study adopted the quantitative research approach. The research design adopted for this study was the cross-sectional survey research design in which the effect of the independent variable on a dependent variable was measured (Cresswell, 2012).

a. Area of the Study

The research area was the Buea municipality in the South West Region of Cameroon. Buea Municipality is located at the foot of Mount Cameroon at an elevation of 1000 m above sea level with a surface area of 870 km² Buea Council (2008). According to the Buea council report (2005), the Buea municipality has an estimated population of above 200,000 inhabitants (BUCREP, 2005) constituting essentially of the Bakweris (indigenes). The urban area includes: Miles 14, 15, 16 and 17, Bomaka, Muea, Molyko, Bonduma, Great Soppo, Clerk's and Federal Quarters, Buea town, GRA, Likoko-Membea, and Bokwaongo.

b. Population of the Study

The population of the study was made up of students in all secondary schools in the Buea Municipality.

i. Target Population

The target population consisted of all students from Four secondary schools which are; Bilingual Grammar School (BGS) Molyko, Government Bilingual High School Muea (GBHS Muea), Summerset Bilingual College (SUBICOL), and Government Technical High School Molyko (GTHS).

ii. Accessible Population

The accessible population of this study was made up of all students from form five, lower sixth and upper sixth of the four secondary schools which were Bilingual Grammar School Molyko, Government Technical High School Molyko, Government Bilingual High School Muea and Summerset Bilingual College Molyko.

Table 1: Accessible Population

Schools	Form Five	Lower Sixth	upper sixth	Total
BGS Molyko	510	310	325	1145
SUBICOL	110	45	120	275
GTHS Molyko	383	212	205	800
GBHS MUEA	35	30	25	90
Total				2310

c. Sampling Technique and Sample Size

i. Sampling Technique

In this study, the simple random sampling technique was used to select 25 respondents from each class and a total of 75 respondents per school.

ii. Sample Size

The sample size was made up of 476 respondents drawn from the three schools taking into consideration sample sized required for a given population size (Krejcie & Morgan, 1970).

The sample size was estimated using sample calculation for one proportion with the formula stated below with the support of Epi-Info 7.0 which has an inbuilt formula for the estimation of sample size for all kind of studies (Social Science and Health/Medical Science). This formula was preferred over of the Kyce and Morgan table 1980 in that their sample size calculation presents the minimum number for every survey study estimated at 1.0 design effect which is no longer that convenient in 21st century research due to series of improvement in the sensitivity of statistical tests which have been modified from 1989 to 2020. In the estimating the sample size and couple with the fact that the students are readily available, a design effect of 1.5 was used to permit the researcher sample a good number of students to ensure better generalization of the findings as well as external validity.

Where:

N=Number of students =

Z= Z value corresponding to the confidence level, =1.96

d= absolute precision =5% (It should be noted that the smaller the precision, the higher the sample size and the more reliable the findings). A precision value of 5% was then considered acceptable for a good statistical significance.

P=expected proportion in the population =50% for optimal sample size estimation.

Design effect=1.5.

Table 2: Distribution of the Accessible Sample

Schools	Form Five	Lower Sixth	upper sixth	Total
BGS Molyko	39	40	40	119
SUBICOL	39	40	40	119
GTHS Molyko	39	40	40	119
GBHS MUEA	39	40	40	119
Total				476

d. Instrument for Data Collection

The instrument for data collection for the study was a questionnaire. The questionnaire items were rated on a four-point modified Likert scale with different statements which measured feelings, beliefs and opinions of students. For each of the statements, respondents were required to state how they feel about each item that is stating whether they strongly agreed (SA), agreed (A), disagreed (D) and strongly disagreed (SD). With regards to the indicators of parenting styles; Section "A" contained items and measures pertaining to authoritarian parenting and students' misconduct. Section "B" contained items and measures pertaining to Permissive parenting and students' misconduct. Section "C" contained items and measures of uninvolved parenting on students' misconduct. With regards to indicators of students' misconduct; Section "D" contained items and measures pertaining to students' misconduct. The statements were rated on a four-point Likert scale (Strongly agreed = 4,

agreed = 3, disagreed = 2 and strongly disagreed = 1. Each of these indicators contained 10 items.

e. Method of Data Analysis

The data collected from the field was first processed using an Excel Spreadsheet whereby, all the participants' responses were keyed, in accordance with each of the test items. After the data were thoroughly checked for possible errors, the quantitative data were analysed using the descriptive and inferential statistical tools. In testing hypotheses of the study, the Chi-Square test incorporated in multi-nominal logistic regression was used because it accommodates categorical variables. In addition, a multiple regression analysis was computed to ascertain the extent all three parenting styles affect students' misconduct and to know specifically, what impact a unit of change for a particular parenting style will have on students' misconduct. The Chi-Square test was equally used to compare categorically how the parenting styles are practice on the students by age and gender.

Decision rule for Testing Hypotheses

The null hypothesis is accepted with the rejection of alternative hypothesis if the calculated p -value is greater than the 0.05, the error margin and the alternative hypothesis is accepted with the rejection of the null hypothesis if the calculated p -value is less than the 0.05, the error margin.

4. Presentation of Findings

The findings are presented based on the specific research questions. The presentation of findings began with the dependent variable (students' misconduct) before the independent variables that constitute the specific objectives of the study. All statistics are presented at 95% confidence interval with error margin set at 0.05. The specific research questions are as follows.

To what extent does authoritarian parenting style affect students' misconduct in secondary schools in Buea Municipality?

How does permissive parenting style affect students' misconduct in secondary schools in Buea Municipality?

To what extent does uninvolved parenting style affect students' misconduct in secondary schools in Buea Municipality?

a. **Research Question One: To What Extent Does Authoritarian Parenting Style Affect Students' Misconduct in Secondary Schools in Buea Municipality?**

Testing of Hypothesis One:

Ho₁: Authoritarian Parenting style has no significant effect on Students' Misconduct in Secondary Schools in Buea Municipality

Ha₁: Authoritarian Parenting style has a significant effect on Students' Misconduct in Secondary Schools in Buea Municipality

Statistically, findings showed that authoritarian parenting style has a significant effect on students' misconduct (p -value $0.000 < 0.05$) and this effect is very strong effect as justified by a very high explanatory power of 0.910 (91%). Therefore, the hypothesis that state authoritarian parenting style has a significant effect on students' misconduct in secondary schools in Buea Municipality was accepted.

b. **Research Question Two: How Does Permissive Parenting Style Affect Students' Misconduct in Secondary Schools in Buea Municipality?**

Testing of Hypothesis Two

Ho₂: Permissive Parenting style has no significant effect on Students' Misconduct in Secondary Schools in Buea Municipality.

Ha₂: Permissive Parenting style has a significant effect on Students' Misconduct in Secondary Schools in Buea Municipality.

Statistically, findings showed that permissive parenting style has a significant effect on students' misconduct (p -value $0.000 < 0.05$) and this effect is very strong effect as justified by a very high explanatory power of 0.885 (88.5%). Therefore, the hypothesis that state permissive parenting style has a significant effect on students' misconduct in secondary schools in Buea Municipality was accepted.

Testing of Hypothesis Three

Ho₃: Uninvolved Parenting style has no significant effect on Students' Misconduct in Secondary Schools in Buea Municipality.

Ha₃: Uninvolved Parenting style has a significant effect on Students' Misconduct in Secondary Schools in Buea Municipality.

Statistically, findings showed that uninvolved parenting style has a significant effect on students' misconduct (p -value $0.000 < 0.05$) and this effect is very strong effect as justified by a very high explanatory power of 0.978 (97.8%). Therefore, the hypothesis that state uninvolved parenting style has a significant effect on students' misconduct in secondary schools in Buea Municipality was accepted.

5. Conclusion, Discussions, Implications, Recommendations and Suggestions for Further Studies

a. Discussion of Findings

The discussion of findings was done in accordance with the specific research objectives. Discussion for each research objective was with the support of the existing literature.

i. Research Objective One: Authoritarian Parenting Style and Students' Misconduct

Statistically, findings revealed that authoritarian parenting style have a significant effect on students' misconduct in the Buea Municipality as majority of the students experience authoritarian parenting style. In conclusion authoritarian parenting style was found to have a significant and very strong effect on students' misconduct. The positive sign of the correlation value implies that students' misconduct increases strongly with constant increase in the use of authoritarian parenting style. Therefore, the hypothesis that state authoritarian parenting style has a significant effect on students' misconduct in secondary schools in Buea Municipality was accepted.

The findings agreed with Diana Baumrind Theory of Parenting Styles (1966). Also, the findings confirm with the study of Agbonna (2013) on parenting styles in Ilorin whose result showed that the parenting styles adopted had influence on the performance of the students. In addition, it was observed that students from Authoritative parenting had better performance than students from other parenting styles.

ii. Research Objective Two: Permissive Parenting Style and Students' Misconduct

Statistically, findings showed that permissive parenting style has a significant and very strong effect on students' misconduct. The positive sign of the correlation value implies that

students' misconduct increases strongly with constant increase in the use of permissive parenting style. Therefore, the hypothesis that state permissive parenting style has a significant effect on students' misconduct in secondary schools in Buea Municipality was accepted.

iii. Research Objective Three: Uninvolved Parenting Style and Students' Misconduct

Statistically, findings showed that uninvolved parenting style has a significant and very strong effect on students' misconduct. The positive sign of the correlation value implies that students' misconduct increases strongly with constant increase in the use of uninvolved parenting style. Students said their parents spend more time at work than at home and they agreed to always solve academic difficulties by themselves because their parents are always busy and hardly follow them up. Equally, some students always return from school before preparing food since parents always leave the house in the morning and return at night which makes them to get tired and have no time to study. Also, students agreed of been allowed to do things they like and their parents do not care about the kind of friends they have and keep. Therefore, the hypothesis that state uninvolved parenting style has a significant effect on students' misconduct in secondary schools in Buea Municipality was accepted

b. Educational Implications

From the findings of this study, parents, teachers, school counsellors and school authorities have much to do. The goal of any educational establishment is to raise students who are useful to themselves, their families being productive and responsible members of the society. To realize this, their conduct is a very crucial component.

Local authorities, school authorities, community heads or traditional leaders have to see to it that they work in synergy with the parents to ensure that they also instil in children's good moral norms, values and customs so as to ensure that children possess moral development and seen as acceptable members of their society which leads to productive learning in school. The main objective of the study was to examine Parenting Styles as an effect on Students' Misconduct in Secondary Schools in the Buea Municipality. This study was guided by three research objectives which were, to find out how Authoritarian, Permissive and Uninvolved Parenting styles affect Students' Misconduct. The study sampled 476 respondents (351 females and 125 males). Data was collected using a closed ended questionnaire. The data was analysed using both inferential and descriptive statistical tools. In testing hypotheses of the study, chi-square was used to determine the effect of the independent variable

(parenting styles) on the dependent variable (Students' misconduct). It was therefore concluded that Parenting Styles affects Students' Misconduct in secondary schools in the Buea Municipality.

c. Recommendations

The findings obtained from data analysis do attest that there is much to be said about Parenting Styles and Students' Misconduct. It is therefore important that parents and educational stakeholders conduct themselves in that which will promote positive moral development. This achievement cannot be realized by the parents alone. Based on the findings, it was recommended that parents should seek for proper parenting styles to train their children. Therefore, the researcher's recommendation in this light is formulated in the form of an appeal to parents, teachers school administrators, counsellors, PTA and to individuals the need for proper conduct and moral development.

d. Suggestions for Further Studies

- The study was carried out in Buea Municipality of the South West Region of Cameroon. The researcher suggests that the sample and population of the study should be wide enough to be carried out in other towns and even regions in the country to give the research more value to be generalized.
- The researcher suggests that each type of parenting style be studied separately to ascertain how much each of them can affect students' misconduct in school.
- Effect of Authoritative parenting on the moral development of students in the Buea Municipality.
- Role of the teacher and its effect on students' Misconduct in secondary schools.
- The Role of the community and its effect on students' Misconduct in Schools.
- The Role of the media and its effect on students' Misconduct in secondary schools in the Buea Municipality.

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